

Anaemia detection from conjunctiva images using deep learning

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15574495>

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Abstract

Anemia is a common blood disorder characterized by a deficiency of red blood cells (RBCs) or haemoglobin, reducing oxygen transport in the body. Traditional diagnostic methods, such as complete blood count (CBC) tests, are time-consuming, require laboratory facilities, and may not be accessible in remote areas. Previous studies have explored automated anemia detection using image processing and machine learning, but they often lack high accuracy or require complex hardware. This project proposes a deep learning-based approach using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to analyze eye conjunctiva images for anemia detection. The system consists of image loading, model building, model training, model evaluation and making prediction with the model modules. The expected outcome is a CNN model with high accuracy (>95%). Model that offers a fast, cost-effective, and non-invasive method for early anemia detection. Future improvements may include integrating with mobile applications, building a region-of-interest extractor that can recognize the parable conjunctiva part of the eye.

Keywords: Anemia, eye conjunctiva, deep learning, convolutional neural networks

Introduction

Anemia is a condition where your blood has a lower-than-normal number of red blood cells or hemoglobin, leading to reduced oxygen transport to the body's tissues, causing symptoms like fatigue and weakness [7, 8]. Early detection of this disease can lead to early diagnosis and treatment of this disease which could save patients health. This project aims to develop a deep learning-based model using convolutional neural network which is trained on conjunctiva images of eye that can predict anemia from non-anemia conditions with more than 95% accuracy. This can lead to a non-invasive, cost effective, time saving alternative for traditional methods.

Traditional methods for detecting anemia includes complete blood count (CBC) test, Peripheral Blood Smear, Iron studies, Vitamin B12 and Folate Test, Reticulocyte count and Bone Marrow Biopsy etc. which require laboratory and are costly. Previous studies have explored automated anemia detection using image processing and machine learning, but they often lack high accuracy or require complex hardware.

This project uses eye conjunctiva dataset from Kaggle (cleaned_augmented_anemia_dataset) which contains about 10,000 images. It is split into three sections training (80% - 8,000 images), validation (10% - 1,000 images) and testing (10% - 1,000 images). A CNN model is trained on training and validation datasets. And is evaluated with the testing dataset on multiple evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, f1 score. After evaluation, the model is used classify on test dataset.

The output of this project is a convolutional neural network [9, 10] model which can detect anemia from eye conjunctiva images with more than 95% accuracy. This can lead to fast, cost-effective, and non-invasive detection of this disease.

Future enhancements for this project include developing an image recognition or region-of-interest extraction system capable of isolating the palpebral conjunctiva from a standard eye image, improving accuracy and automation. Additionally, implementing the model as a mobile application would enhance accessibility, allowing real-time anemia detection in remote or resource-limited areas.

Literature survey

Various non-invasive methods to predict anemia has been explored in the past each with their limitation.

S. S. Rasheed *et al.* (2022) ^[1] proposed a machine learning-based framework for diagnosing eight medical conditions, including anemia. The study used real-world data from 1000 patients at Al-Kadhimiya Teaching Hospital. Several machine learning algorithms were applied, including SVM, Decision Tree, KNN, and Naïve Bayes. These models were used for multi-class classification based on patient symptoms. However, the study's main limitation was its dependence on structured medical data and its relatively low accuracy of 84%.

A. Gupta *et al.* (2022) ^[2] developed a machine learning-based system for early disease prediction using patient symptoms, age, and gender. The dataset included symptoms for 230 diseases, and four algorithms were tested: Weighted Decision Tree, Random Forest, Naïve Bayes, and K-Nearest Neighbour. The highest accuracy achieved was 93.5%, aiming to reduce hospital workload. However, the system relies only on symptom-based inputs, lacking medical imaging or lab results, which may affect its ability to diagnose conditions like anemia. Additionally, the study does not explain its validation method or address dataset bias, limiting its generalizability.

Mythili N. *et al.* (2025) ^[3] proposed a web-based application that uses deep learning models like ResNet50, EfficientNet B9, and DenseNet169 to detect anemia from fingernail images. The system provides a non-invasive alternative to blood tests by analyzing visual signs of anemia in nail appearance. It is designed for use on smartphones and laptops, making it accessible in remote or underserved areas. Features like email authentication and data encryption ensure user privacy and security. However, the study faces limitations related to image quality, lighting variations, and differences in nail appearance, which may affect diagnostic accuracy.

C. Viveha *et al.* (2024) ^[4] developed a smartphone-based, non-invasive screening tool for early anemia detection using fingernail images. The system analyzes nail bed coloration to estimate hemoglobin levels through machine learning methods like ridge regression, lasso regression, and a deep learning model, EfficientNet. EfficientNet outperformed other models with the lowest error rates (RMSE of 0.65 and MAE of 0.624). This highlights the effectiveness of deep learning in identifying visual patterns linked to anemia. However, the study's dataset was imbalanced, with significantly more anemia images than non-anemia ones, which may lead to biased predictions and increased false positives.

A. Tamir *et al.* (2017) ^[5] proposed a non-invasive method for detecting anemia using images of the anterior conjunctiva of the eye. The method is based on analyzing the RGB color spectrum in images to correlate red and green light reflection with hemoglobin levels. Images are captured via smartphone under controlled lighting, and computer-based image processing is used to classify anemia based on set thresholds. The system achieved 78.9%

accuracy in distinguishing anemia from non-anemia individuals. However, despite its potential, the accuracy is still lower compared to standard blood tests.

V. R. Ravi *et al.* (2024) ^[6] conducted a comparative study on anemia estimation using eye conjunctival images, evaluating traditional CNN and EfficientNet models. While the CNN achieved around 85% accuracy, EfficientNet-B2 reached an impressive 99.7%, showcasing its superior performance. The study attributes this to EfficientNet's compound scaling, which effectively captures subtle variations in conjunctival images. However, limitations include the lack of details on dataset size, diversity, and validation methods, raising concerns about generalizability. Additionally, the extremely high accuracy may indicate overfitting, suggesting a need for further validation in real-world scenarios.

This project addresses many of these limitations by using a balanced and augmented dataset of 10,000 conjunctiva images and a CNN-based model evaluated with standard performance metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. By focusing on conjunctival imaging alone, this work ensures a non-invasive, high-accuracy approach (95% +), while remaining cost-effective, scalable.

Proposed methodology

The proposed methodology aims to predict anemia from parable conjunctiva images to warn patients if they have anemia in early stages. This methodology consists of five modules. The goal of this project is to build a deep learning model which is of ease of access to the people and physicians.

Data preparation was done on dataset that was loaded from Kaggle. This dataset contains augmented images of conjunctiva(eye), fingernails and palm. But this project only uses images of conjunctiva. The conjunctiva is a thin, transparent membrane that covers the white part of the eye (sclera) and the inner surface of the eyelids, playing a crucial role in protecting and lubricating the eye, which turns pale if a patient has anemia. This dataset contains only augmented images.

A convolutional neural network was built using TensorFlow library. This convolutional neural network works by extracting features from the input and using them to update weights and biases to the fully connected neural network at the end of the convolution stack and using this learned information to make predictions on unseen data. The attributes of these CNNs are changed and noted after each training for improvement. Typically, all of them are trained over 10, 100, and 200 epochs, with the same dataset and same number of convolutional layers (3) but different number of layers in ANN after the convolution stack, different activation functions in that ANN.

The final output will be decided from the single neuron in the output layer. Which is between 0 and 1(0 for anemia, 1 for non anemia). Then in the third module the trained models are assessed based on different metrics to know their performance.

Fig 1: Dataflow diagram

A. Module 1: Data Loading

Data was loaded from Kaggle. The name of the set is: cleaned_augmented_anemia_dataset which contains images of conjunctiva (eye), fingernails and palm. All these images are of size 224x224 pixels and augmented. Data augmentation is the process of changing the properties of data without changing the underlying meaning to produce mode data. All images in this dataset are randomly rotated, rescaled, height and width shifted, zoomed, horizontally flipped to get more data which enables model to learn more by providing more data. There were 10,256 conjunctiva images in total which was split into 3 for training, validating and testing as show in table 1.

Table 1: Table shows number of images for different datasets

Data	Class	Image count
Training	Anemia	4,219
	Non-Anemia	4,037
Validation	Anemia	500
	Non-Anemia	500
Testing	Anemia	500
	Non-Anemia	500

B. Module 2: Model Building

After loading the dataset, a Convolutional neural network (CNN) was built using TensorFlow library. The functional API is used to define the number of layers in the neural network. The model contains some constant features such as 3 convolutional layers with ReLU activation function, with valid padding, kernel size of (2, 2), input size of (224x224x3), convolutional stride of (1, 1). And also come variable features for comparison such as the number of ANN layers after the convolutional layers, different activation functions for ANNs and different number of epochs while training (as shown in Figure 2). These different attributes result in models with different performances.

Fig 2: Convolutional Neural Network architecture for model number 4 from Table: 3

C. Module 3: Model Training

After the architecture is defined, each model is trained using the training dataset with a fixed batch size of 32. Unless otherwise specified, all models are trained for 200 epochs. The objective of training is to optimize the model's ability to correctly classify images by minimizing the loss and maximizing classification accuracy. The training process uses the Adam optimizer due to its adaptive learning rate capabilities and efficient convergence. The binary cross-entropy loss function is used, which is appropriate for binary classification tasks such as anemia detection. To monitor performance, training and validation metrics-including accuracy and loss-are recorded after each epoch for evaluation.

Adam optimizer

The Adam optimizer, short for "Adaptive Moment Estimation," is an iterative optimization algorithm used to minimize the loss function during the training of neural networks. Adam can be looked at as a combination of RMSprop (Root Mean Square Propagation) and Stochastic Gradient Descent with momentum [11].

Binary cross entropy (BCE)

BCE (also called as log loss) is a loss function used in binary classification problems where target variable has two possible outcomes, 0 & 1 and it measures the performance of the model whose output is a probability value between 0 and 1 [12].

$$L = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i \log(p_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - p_i)]$$

N – Number of samples in the dataset (batch size)

y – Actual label (1 or 0)

p – Predicted probability (between 1 and 0)

D. Module 4: Evaluating Model

After training the model with the training dataset, the model is evaluated with the testing data to identify its performance. Various evaluation metrics are used for this process such as:

Accuracy Score

Accuracy score is the ratio of correctly predicted Instances to total instances.

$$A = \frac{\text{Number of correct predictions}}{\text{Total number of predictions}} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

Precision Score

Precision is the ratio of true positive (TP) predictions to total positive predictions (TP + FP).

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Recall Score

Recall (or sensitivity) is the ratio of true positive predictions to all actual positives (TP + FN).

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

F1 Score

F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, balancing the two.

$$f1 = 2 \times \frac{\text{precision} \times \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}}$$

E. Module 5: Making predictions

After evaluating the model, the model is used for predicting from testing data (unseen data) and the results are plotted on a graph Fig. 3.

Fig 3: Predictions made by model number 4 from Table 2

Results and analysis

Table 1 represents the initial training of models with same number of convolutional layers (3) with a single layer in ANN with 100 neurons and an output layer with single neuron trained over different number of epochs: 10, 100, 200. From the results we see that model (number 3) trained over 200 epochs performs better than others while evaluating.

Table 2: Models evaluation based on number of epochs

Model	No. of epochs	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
1	10	0.563	0.535	0.962	0.687
2	100	0.54	0.56	0.38	0.45
3	200	0.97	0.98	0.95	0.97

Chart 1: Performance metrics by number of Epoch

Table 2 and chart 1 represents the difference in their scoring metrics when the number of layers in the ANN (after the convolutional layers stack). Each model from this table contains same number of convolutional layers – 3. But different numbers of layers in the ANN – 1, 2, 3 all with 100 neurons each without considering the output layer (which is constant with a single neuron). And all these models are also trained over 200 epochs because it provides a model that learns better features from images – as seen from table 2. From this table 2 we can see that model (number 4) with 2 hidden layers in its ANN performs better than others.

Table 3: Models evaluation based on number of layers in ANN.

Model	No. of layers in ANN	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
3	1	0.97	0.98	0.95	0.97
4	2	0.991	0.986	0.996	0.99
5	3	0.981	0.974	0.988	0.981

Chart 2: Performance metrics by number of ANN Layers

Table 3 and chart 2 represents the difference in model(s) performance based on the activation function used in the ANN layer(s). In this comparison each model contains 2 layers of 100 neurons each in the ANN which was chosen to be better than others from Table 2. The activation functions used are: Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), Hyperbolic Tangent (Tanh), and softmax. From the results of this table 2.2 we can conclude that model (number 4) with 3 convolutional layers and 2 hidden layers with ReLU as activation function performs best for classifying anemia in this dataset with 99% accuracy.

Table 3: Models performance based on activation function in ANN

Model	Activation function	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
4	ReLU	0.991	0.986	0.996	0.99
6	Tanh	0.988	0.982	0.994	0.988
7	softmax	0.943	0.901	0.994	0.945

Chart 3: Performance metrics by Activation function

Conclusion

This study assesses performance – accuracy – of convolutional neural network with different attributes for classifying anemia from non-anemia eye conjunctiva images. Concluding from above tables (table 1, 2, 3) that the model number 4 which has three convolutional layers, two hidden layers in ANN with ReLU activation and an output layer performs better yielding 99% accuracy on test dataset. The future enhancements of this project may include building a mobile/web application that is also capable of extracting region-of-interest from a regular eye image which can improve automation and user experience of this project.

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